

Incorporation of waste glass dust with pigments containing Cd, S, and Se into magnesium oxychloride cement for sustainable production using 3D printing

Mária Kolářová^a , Anna-Marie Lauermannová^b,
Martina Záleská^{b,c} , Christos G. Aneziris^d,
Jana Hubalkova^d , Ondřej Jankovský^{b,e}

^a Department of Glass and Ceramics, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 5, 6, 166 28, Prague, Czech Republic

^b Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 5, 6, 166 28, Praha, Czech Republic

^c Department of Materials Engineering and Chemistry, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Thákurova 7, 166 29, Prague, Czech Republic

^d Institute of Ceramics, Refractories and Composite Materials, TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Agricolastr. 17, 09599, Freiberg, Germany

^e Materialový a Metalurgický Výzkum S.r.o., Pohraniční 693/31, Vítkovice, 703 00, Ostrava, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the incorporation of ultra-fine coloured waste glass containing cadmium, sulphur, and selenium pigments into magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) formulations for sustainable construction applications, including evaluating the preparation feasibility of the cementitious paste for subsequent 3D printing development. The glass waste, in the form of fine powder originating from red glass bead production, was added to MOC mixtures in varying amounts (3%, 6%, and 9%). The composites were evaluated for structural, mechanical, thermal, and environmental performance. Results showed that the addition of glass dust had minimal impact on porosity, thermal properties, and colour of the cement, while slightly improving compressive strength and water resistance. Microstructural analysis confirmed the presence of dense intergrown MOC phase 5 crystals, and leachability tests indicated negligible environmental risk. It was demonstrated that the material can be produced using 3D printing, and the setting time increases slightly with a higher glass dust content. The findings demonstrate the feasibility of reusing specialised industrial waste in high-performance, eco-friendly construction materials.

1. Introduction

Sustainability and circular economy principles have become key pillars of modern industrial material processing. Recycling waste materials offers an alternative resource stream, helping to mitigate the depletion of natural raw materials and supporting the development of novel composite materials with comparable functional properties. This approach not only enhances resource efficiency and reduces waste but also fosters innovation in material engineering and product design, aligning with contemporary environmental

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: pavlikz@fsv.cvut.cz (Z. Pavlík).

and economic objectives.

The construction industry is among the largest consumers of natural sand, particularly as a fine aggregate in cementitious mixtures, highlighting the urgent need to identify suitable alternative materials. Globally, millions of tons of glass waste are generated annually due to population growth and widespread daily consumption. As a non-biodegradable solid waste, glass poses a significant environmental burden. Recycling glass is therefore essential to reduce its ecological impact. The use of glass powder as a partial replacement for fine aggregate in cement offers both economic and environmental benefits [1–3]. Environmental management systems have been implemented in many companies, including leading global glass manufacturers such as Preciosa, a Czech producer of decorative glass, beads, and glass chandeliers [4,5].

Numerous studies have demonstrated that finely ground recycled glass powder can significantly enhance the mechanical properties of concrete and cementitious composites, primarily due to its pozzolanic activity and high silica content. Replacing up to 20% of cement with glass powder or fibres has been shown to improve compressive, tensile, and flexural strength, with optimal performance typically observed at replacement levels between 10% and 20% [6–12].

Although most available research focuses on traditional Portland cement, the pozzolanic mechanisms and micro-filler effects of waste glass are also relevant to magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) [13–16]. This type of binder offers specific advantages, such as low energy consumption during production and rapid strength development, and is increasingly being explored in the context of sustainable construction materials. Fine glass particles contribute to matrix densification, reduced permeability, and improved paste-to-aggregate bonding, all of which enhance mechanical performance. Our recent study [17] demonstrated that the addition of ground glass cullet as a filler in MOC composites could significantly improve their mechanical properties while also contributing to a reduced environmental footprint of the production process. The results show that glass cullet not only enhances strength parameters but also supports cleaner production by partially replacing natural glass sands with recycled content. These findings confirm the potential of glass as a functional filler even in alternative cement systems such as MOC.

Recent advances in additive manufacturing using the material extrusion 3D printing method have opened new pathways for the application of sustainable composites [18–28]. 3D printing is increasingly used in construction, with recent focus on 3D concrete printing and material advancements. Literature suggests 3D-printed structures can be more cost-effective than traditional methods due to optimised design and reduced labour [29–33]. 3D printing of cementitious materials offers advantages in design flexibility, material efficiency, and construction speed. The integration of recycled glass into printable cement-based mixtures represents a promising strategy to improve both environmental and mechanical performance. Studies by Vidakis et al. [34] and Petousis et al. [35] presented that the morphology, size, and distribution of glass particles significantly influence the mechanical behaviour of polymer composites in material extrusion 3D printing. Specifically, Petousis et al. [35] applied 3, 6, and 9 wt% of ground red glass shards into isotactic polypropylene matrices, demonstrating that even small additions of coloured glass waste can affect the engineering response of the printed material. These findings suggest that similar principles may apply to cementitious systems, where crushed glass could enhance both structural integrity and printability.

Furthermore, Boleslavsky et al. [36] emphasise the importance of optimising printing parameters and understanding the interaction between material composition and process conditions. Their work on ceramic 3D printing highlights the critical role of rheology, interlayer bonding, and dimensional stability - factors that are equally relevant when incorporating glass fillers into cement-based filaments.

This study focuses on the valorisation of ultra-fine coral-coloured glass waste generated during the production of red glass beads. The potential valorisation of a specific red glass dust residue derived from the Preciosa Rocailles bead manufacturing process is suggested. This material, composed of glass tubes rejected for colour inconsistencies post-processing, currently constitutes an unused waste product that is sent to landfills. Although this is not a high-volume waste stream, it presents a unique challenge due to its distinctive chemical composition, including the presence of cadmium and selenium, which are used as colourants. These elements pose environmental risks and complicate recycling, and therefore identifying sustainable applications for this material is both necessary and innovative. The primary objective is to incorporate this specific type of glass waste into MOC formulations without compromising mechanical or rheological properties, nor causing adverse environmental effects, and to evaluate its suitability for 3D printing applications. The overarching aim is to determine whether this niche but environmentally challenging waste stream can be transformed into a functional micro-filler that maintains or enhances composite properties while enabling its use in advanced applications. This research aims to demonstrate that even specialised, small-scale industrial waste can be effectively reused in advanced construction materials, contributing to both sustainability and innovation in material design.

2. Experimental

2.1. Characterisation of input raw materials

The following raw materials to produce MOC-based samples with different colour hues caused by the addition of glass colour dust were used: **coral-coloured glass dust (CGD)**, conventional magnesium-based raw materials for Sorel cement (magnesium oxide, magnesium chloride hexahydrate), and sand (PG) as the principal filler.

2.1.1. Waste CGD

During the grinding process of waste shards from the production of glass beads (see Fig. 1), several fractions are obtained that can be used as recyclate, e.g., in the production of glass-ceramics [17,37]. The tested waste CGD makes the finest fraction obtained during this process. The processed glass fraction was passed through a 50 µm mesh sieve and analysed – the relevant parameters are listed in

Table 1. The distribution curve measured by LD is shown in Fig. 1, right. The longitudinal shape of the sharp-edged particles influences the shape of the distribution curve, and especially the upper limit (100 μm). Most of the particles are not isometric, and some micro-shards have a length-to-width ratio of up to 5:1. The surface of the particles documents the ongoing brittle fracture during glass crushing.

The CGD is primarily composed of soda-potash glass, with boron and calcium admixtures. The EDS map in Fig. 2, bottom, demonstrates the homogeneity of individual element distribution in CGD, where all major components, such as Si, Na, K, and the colouring elements Cd, Zn, and Se, are evenly distributed throughout the entire volume. The colouration is obtained through the combination of selenium, cadmium, zinc, and sulphur, as emphasised by the yellow highlighting of the corresponding values in Table 2. SEM analysis (Fig. 2 top) shows the morphology of CGD particles. The fineness of these particles induces the reduced permeability and porosity of the resulting composites, discussed later in the paper.

Phase composition measurements (XRD) of CGD proved the presence of two compounds, cadmium selenide sulphide (ICDD 04-020-5584) and zinc cadmium selenium (ICDD 04-003-9925). Fig. 3 shows the diffraction pattern of CGD. The main reflections of both phases are located at very close positions of 2θ , and therefore, it is not possible to unequivocally determine whether they are two crystalline phases or a solid solution. However, reflections at 24.45, 25.99, and 27.76 $^{\circ}2\theta$ (see the detail in Fig. 3) could be associated with both. Cadmium selenide sulphide is the primary component responsible for the intense red colour produced by this combination.

2.1.2. Silica sand (PG)

A combination of three size fractions of silica sand (Filtrační písky, spol. s r.o., Czech Republic), namely PG1 (0–0.5 mm), PG2 (0.5–1 mm), and PG3 (1–2 mm), was used as a filler, see Fig. 4.

2.1.3. Magnesium-based raw materials

The magnesium sources were powdered magnesium oxide (MgO, 98% purity, Penta, s.r.o., Czech Republic) and magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, analytical grade, Lach-ner, s.r.o., Czech Republic).

2.2. Sample preparation procedure

The raw material mixture composition was calculated in order to form MOC Phase 5 as a matrix filled with 3 fractions of PG and CGD. Raw materials were weighed according to the proportions listed in Table 3. The reference mixture contained only raw materials for MOC sand. The amounts of CGD in the other three mixtures (3%, 6%, and 9% wt) and labelling are consistent with the authors' previous publication concerning graphene-based cementitious additives [38] and with studies focused on processing the same type of waste for 3D printing using a polymer matrix [33].

The mixing procedure for the MOC-REF sample took place according to the following steps. First, a solution of $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water was prepared. Then it was added to a planetary mixer together with MgO powder. The suspension was mixed for 30 s in a planetary mixer at a low speed (140 rpm). Mixing continued for an additional 30 s at low speed and then for 4 min at a high speed (285 rpm). The mixing procedure for CGD-modified samples was similar; however, before adding the individual components to the planetary mixer, MgO and CGD were premixed for 30 s at a low speed. The mixture preparation procedure resulted in homogeneous suspensions, which were poured into moulds measuring $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm. The prism-shaped samples were demoulded after 24 h and placed in a laboratory ($T = 23 \pm 2$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $RH = 50 \pm 5$ %), where they were tempered for 27 days. Some of the mixtures were used to verify the possibility of 3D printing. The CGD-modified MOC composites production process is schemed in Fig. 5.

Table 4 provides an overview of the physical characteristics of glass dust. The compaction significantly increased the density of the powder samples. The specific density was determined using the helium pycnometry method.

Thermal properties recorded for uncompacted and fully compacted CGD are summarised in Table 5. Similarly, as observed for powder density, the thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity were distinctly enhanced by compaction, with full compaction achieved in 240 s.

Fig. 1. Waste glass beads (left), the finest fraction after grinding of waste glass beads (middle), and their particle size distribution (right).

Table 1
Distribution of particles in CGD.

	D ₁₀ (μm)	D ₅₀ (μm)	D ₉₀ (μm)	Specific surface area (m ² ·kg ⁻¹)
Mean	7.46 ± 0.103	20.9 ± 0.165	41.7 ± 0.343	421.9 ± 3.341
Min	7.32	20.6	41.2	418.1
Max	7.60	21.1	42.3	426.6

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of CGD (top) with elemental maps of major elements (bottom).

2.3. Methods and instruments

Details on the used analytical methods and instruments are summarised in the Supporting **Information** file.

3. RESULTS and discussion

The prepared composite samples (MOC-CGD and MOC-REF) were subjected to a series of analyses after a 28-day curing period (Fig. 6).

The basic macro- and microstructural characteristics presented in Table 6 demonstrate a correlation with the compositional

Table 2

Chemical composition of waste coral-coloured glass dust (CGD) in wt.%.

B ₂ O ₃	F	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	SO ₃	Cl	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	ZnO	SeO ₂	ZrO ₂	MoO ₃	CdO	Cr ₂ O ₃	Rb ₂ O
1.40	0.76	18.84	1.17	0.48	62.63	0.31	0.06	5.34	2.38	0.03	0.27	5.67	0.12	0.01	0.01	0.47	0.01	0.01

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of CGD.

Fig. 4. Microphotographs of silica sand fractions: PG1 (0–0.5 mm), PG2 (0.5–1 mm), PG3 (1–2 mm).

Table 3

Batch composition of CGD-modified MOC samples.

	Sorel cement (g)			Filler (g)			Additive component	
	MgO	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	H ₂ O	Silica sand			CGD (g)	Ratio of added CGD (wt.%)
				PG1 0–0.5 mm	PG2 0.5–1 mm	PG3 1–2 mm		
MOC-REF	700.08	706.26	438.09	700.08	700.08	700.08	-	-
MOC-CGD-3	700.08	706.26	438.09	700.08	700.08	700.08	55.33	3
MOC-CGD-6	700.08	706.26	438.09	700.08	700.08	700.08	109.65	6
MOC-CGD-9	700.08	706.26	438.09	700.08	700.08	700.08	166.00	9

variations of the samples. With increasing content of CGD, the bulk density decreased very slightly, as glass has a lower density than sand. The very low decrease in values is due to the glass content varying only slightly, within a range of 1.2% to 4.2%. Similarly, porosity did not change significantly, as the fine CGD added into the prepared mixtures helped to refine the matrix of the composites, which correlates well with the increased specific density of MOC-CGD materials. Total open pore volume followed the trend of the total open porosity data. The highest differences were observed in average pore radii, whose values corresponded with the shape of pore size distribution curves graphed in Fig. 7. The MOC-CGD-9 sample exhibited the smallest average pore size, with no notable difference compared to the MOC-REF and MOC-CGD-3 samples. Conversely, MOC-CGD-6 had the largest average pore diameter, correlating with its highest porosity. The MOC-CGD-9 sample also featured a larger quantity of gel pores, which offset the reduced capillary pore volume in relation to the MOC-CGD-3 composite. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the variations in porosity among the materials studied were negligible, resulting in only minor alterations to the mechanical and thermal properties of the composites discussed below.

The mechanical properties of the composites are listed in Table 7, with a graphical representation in Fig. 8. A minor enhancement in compressive strength was noted for the MOC-CGD-3 and MOC-CGD-6 composites compared to the control sample MOC-REF. For the remaining samples and studied parameters, no substantial differences in mechanical properties were detected between the MOC-CGD composites and the reference material. These variations typically fell within the standard deviation range, consistent with the previously discussed structural parameters. The inclusion of CGD did not actively influence the chemical and crystalline composition of the composites, i.e., no reactivity of CGD with MOC was proven; however, CGD served as a micro-filler, refining the composite matrix microstructure, as indicated by the increased matrix density values. In terms of strength, the acquired values were sufficiently high,

Fig. 5. A scheme of the CGD-modified MOC composites production process.

Table 4

Physical and thermal properties of coral-coloured glass dust (CGD).

Sample	Powder density uncompactd ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Powder density fully compacted ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Blaine fineness ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)	Specific density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
CGD	755.5	1233.2	279.75	2558.1

Table 5

Thermal properties of coral-coloured glass dust (CGD).

Sample	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Volumetric heat capacity ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Thermal diffusivity ($\text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
CGD - uncompactd	0.081	0.353	0.228
CGD - fully compactd	0.140	0.719	0.194

allowing the tested materials to be used as structural components for load-bearing structures, prefabricated elements, industrial flooring, facing slabs, and similar applications. The compressive strength of all examined MOC composites aligns with that of high-strength concrete [39]. The results presented in Table 7 are highly promising for the recycling and development strategy, particularly in terms of maintaining or even improving the mechanical performance of composites incorporating waste material – CGD. However, for the practical application of MOC-CGD composites as structural, load-bearing materials, further investigations and analyses, such as creep behaviour, must be conducted in future research. The incorporation of CGD also led to a slight improvement in water resistance, as evidenced by an increase in the softening coefficient. This enhancement is likely associated with more efficient packing of the composite structure containing CGD, resulting in higher specific density and a greater volume of gel phase and fine capillary pores compared to the reference material MOC-REF. Since the rate of moisture ingress into the porous matrix influences potential material degradation, a 24-h one-dimensional water absorption test was conducted. The water uptake was reduced from approximately 3.1% for MOC-REF to 2.5% for all CGD-modified composites.

The understanding of the strength development of construction materials over time is critical for processing and construction scheduling. Therefore, the 7-day compressive strength data were additionally measured. The 7-day compressive strength is presented in Table 8. The differences in the 7-day and 28-day compressive strength values vary in the range from 4.2% (MOC-CGD-6) to 4.5% (MOC-CGD-3). Based on the work published by Huang et al. [40], the compressive strength of MOC-based composites is considered to

Fig. 6. MOC samples after demoulding (left to right).

Table 6
Basic macro- and microstructural properties of MOC-CGD and MOC-REF.

	Matrix density ρ_{mat} ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Bulk density ρ_b ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Total open porosity ϕ (%)	Open pore volume V_{op} ($\text{cm}^{-3}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	Average pore diameter d_a (μm)
MOC-REF	2264.35 ± 1.03	2053.14 ± 1.35	9.16 ± 0.42	0.0480	0.0363
MOC-CGD-3	2268.50 ± 1.01	2049.11 ± 1.73	9.54 ± 0.27	0.0499	0.0318
MOC-CGD-6	2276.51 ± 0.93	2043.58 ± 1.09	10.23 ± 0.05	0.0632	0.0467
MOC-CGD-9	2285.06 ± 1.04	2054.61 ± 1.96	10.09 ± 0.09	0.0543	0.0301

Fig. 7. Pore size distribution: a) cumulative curves; b) distribution curves.

Table 7
Mechanical properties of MOC with CGD after 28 days.

	Flexural strength f_f (MPa)	Compressive strength f_c (MPa)	Young's modulus E_d (GPa)	Softening coefficient α_s (%)
MOC-REF	17.36 ± 0.59	71.45 ± 3.50	36.17 ± 0.99	75.13 ± 3.75
MOC-CGD-3	17.64 ± 0.64	76.67 ± 5.18	36.72 ± 0.57	80.57 ± 5.21
MOC-CGD-6	17.54 ± 0.96	73.78 ± 1.99	36.10 ± 0.90	78.27 ± 2.13
MOC-CGD-9	17.52 ± 0.13	71.70 ± 7.16	35.93 ± 0.48	78.77 ± 7.45

Fig. 8. Graphical representation of mechanical parameters tested.

reach maxima within 10-14 days. Therefore, regarding the issue of strength development in time, the obtained mechanical parameters measured for 28-day samples can be considered as final, and no significant changes in time are expected.

The thermal parameters of composites are presented in Table 9. The incorporation of CGD into the cured composites exhibited a negligible effect on their thermal properties. No discernible trend was observed in the thermal property values, and the differences among the materials tested were minimal, typical within the range of standard deviation. The thermal properties of composites containing CGD could potentially be influenced by two factors: a) variations in the thermal parameters of CGD compared to silica sand, namely the inherent thermal properties of CGD; b) alterations in the porosity and density of the composites arising from the inclusion of CGD as a constituent in the composite mixtures. Although the thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity of CGD are lower than those of silica sand [41], their impact on the overall thermal performance of the composites was minimal due to the low proportion of CGD used. Furthermore, the reduced heat transfer capability and heat storage capacity of CGD were offset by the enhanced packing of the composite constituents, as evidenced by the increased specific density. In conclusion, considering the measurement uncertainties, the evaluated thermal properties of the composites can be regarded as similar.

A comparison of the fracture surfaces of the MOC samples modified with CGD with those of the reference sample is shown in Fig. 9. On detailed examination, the fracture surfaces of all samples exhibited a similarly dense and homogeneous structure without obvious CGD agglomerates or phase separations, confirming the above-mentioned basic micro- and macrostructural properties (Table 6). The CGD-modified MOC samples did not show increased porosity or visible microcracks, indicating effective dispersion of glass dust within the matrix. Furthermore, a negligible influence on the overall colouration observed was insufficient to affect the visual assessment of the MOC composite integrity, supporting the conclusion that the addition of glass dust does not affect the aesthetic or structural properties of the CGD-modified MOC composites.

Table 10 presents the chemical composition of CGD-modified MOC samples in comparison to the reference. The CGD-modified MOC samples differ primarily in the content of the main MOC component (MgO) from magnesium input materials, which systematically decreases as a result of increasing addition of CGD.

The maintenance of visual properties was supported by colorimetric data presented in Table 11. If the aim is to achieve a terracotta-like colouration on the surface of the prepared MOC samples modified with CGD, which are otherwise grey, this could be accomplished by surface polishing. This effect is most pronounced in polished MOC samples containing 9 wt% of CGD, as shown in Table 11 and Fig. 10. The enhanced colour saturation achieved through surface refinement not only improves the aesthetic qualities of MOC composites but also demonstrates the potential of surface treatment techniques to modify the visual appearance of MOC-based materials for architectural or decorative applications. Values of total difference ΔE^* in Table 11 confirm substantial improvement beyond subtle changes. Polishing induced substantial colour shifts with ΔE^* values of 15–18, exceeding established colour science thresholds

Table 8
Compressive strength of MOC with CGD after 7 days.

	Compressive strength f_c (MPa)
MOC-REF	68.38 ± 3.25
MOC-CGD-3	73.22 ± 3.28
MOC-CGD-6	70.31 ± 2.54
MOC-CGD-9	68.62 ± 3.10

Table 9

Thermal properties of MOC with CGD after 28 days.

	Thermal conductivity λ_d ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Thermal diffusivity α ($\text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	Volumetric heat capacity c_v ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)
MOC-REF	2.318 ± 0.030	1.075 ± 0.039	2.226 ± 0.011
MOC-CGD-3	2.328 ± 0.013	1.094 ± 0.042	2.132 ± 0.068
MOC-CGD-6	2.300 ± 0.022	1.116 ± 0.031	2.063 ± 0.065
MOC-CGD-9	2.351 ± 0.024	1.087 ± 0.047	2.167 ± 0.010

Fig. 9. Fracture surfaces of MOC samples with added colorant: the referent sample MOC-REF and MOC-CGD-3, MOC-CGD-6, MOC-CGD-9.**Table 10**

Chemical composition of samples of MOC with CGD in wt.%.

	MgO	CaO	SiO ₂	Cl	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃	ZnO	CdO	Sum to 100%
MOC-REF	33	0.04	54	12	0.6	-	0.03	0.3	-	-	0.113
MOC-CGD-3	31	0.10	57	11	0.16	0.1	0.14	0.3	0.11	0.01	0.104
MOC-CGD-6	31	0.1	57	11	0.17	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.02	0.125
MOC-CGD-9	29	0.2	59	10	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.03	0.175

($\Delta E^* > 3.3\text{--}6$ for perceptible changes per CIE Lab* standards). These shifts characterised by reduced L^* (lightness) and elevated a^* , b^* align with perceptual enhancements toward warmer, more vibrant tones, corresponding to architectural facade where surface finishing elevates material depth and visual harmony. The resulting polished MOC samples exhibit colour changes that are highly attractive and relevant for contemporary interior design applications. Nevertheless, the optimal CGD content for aesthetic purposes cannot be considered universal. The aesthetic effect depends on the intended application and the required structural performance. While the 9 wt% CGD sample exhibited the most pronounced colour enhancement after polishing (highest ΔE and increased a^* , b^* values), lower CGD contents provided slightly better mechanical performance. Therefore, the practical selection of CGD content represents a balance between visual appearance and structural requirements of the given construction element.

The phase composition of the samples was analysed using XRD. The results of quantitative XRD analysis are summarised in Table 12. Individual X-ray diffraction patterns, shown in Fig. 11, provide detailed information about the crystalline phases present in the samples. The results show that the addition of the colouring agent in the form of glass dust has no significant effect on the phase composition of the final composites. Quantitative phase analysis confirmed the predicted increase in the amorphous fraction with increasing additive content. All samples showed the presence of the desired matrix phase, MOC Phase 5 (ICDD 04-014-8836), quartz originating from the sand filler (ICDD 01-075-8322), and chlorartinite (ICDD 00-061-0391), which is a chlorocarbonate phase forming on the MOC Phase 5 surface through carbon dioxide sequestration [42].

The microstructure of the prepared composites was investigated using SEM (Fig. 12). All samples displayed the characteristic

Table 11
Colorimetric data of the MOC-based composite samples with CGD.

	Measured surface	Specular component	Colour values			8° gloss	ΔE^*
			L*(D65)	a*(D65)	b*(D65)		
MOC-REF		SCI	79.52	-0.05	0.92	7	15.29
		SCE	79.34	-0.04	0.95	7	
		SCI	67.11	5.36	13.32	103	
		SCE	63.53	5.86	15.01	103	
MOC-CGD-3		SCI	78.67	0.56	2.33	5	15.00
		SCE	78.54	0.57	2.38	5	
		SCI	65.52	6.33	12.96	95	
		SCE	62.11	6.88	14.49	95	
MOC-CGD-6		SCI	77.33	0.62	1.83	5	18.41
		SCE	77.21	0.62	1.87	5	
		SCI	60.97	8.07	13.42	98	
		SCE	56.97	8.92	15.51	98	
MOC-CGD-9		SCI	77.21	0.62	1.87	5	18.60
		SCE	73.67	0.99	4.17	5	
		SCI	60.26	7.96	12.43	100	
		SCE	56.10	8.87	14.47	100	

needle-like morphology of the MOC Phase 5 crystals, which are the main crystalline phase. The detailed study of the morphology revealed the intergrowth of these needles, resulting in a dense microstructure that contributed to the improved mechanical performance of the composites described in [Tables 6 and 7](#)

Fracture surface was also studied for the distribution of the present elements through EDS, resulting in elemental maps presented in [Fig. 13](#). All samples show the presence of the MOC Phase 5 elements (Mg, Cl, and O) and the map of Si with well-distinguishable silica sand particles. The sample containing the highest proportion of CGD, MOC-CGD-9, also showed the presence of Na originating from the glassy phases in CGD.

A micro focus X-ray computer tomography was used to evaluate the homogeneity and distribution of silica sand. The micrographs shown in [Fig. 14](#) confirmed the same homogeneity in all samples of CGD-modified MOC. Due to the limited resolution of the performed CT scans (voxel size: 9 μm), neither gel nor capillary pores can be quantitatively evaluated. CT scans revealed a closed porosity within the silica sand grains, which cannot be intruded by mercury during the MIP measurements, cf. [Fig. 7](#).

Leachability of Cd, Se, and Zn from the prepared MOC-based composites with CGD was studied, and the obtained values are presented in [Table 13](#). Leaching measurements were conducted after 24 h and after 7 days of curing. ICP-OES analysis revealed that the most significant leaching occurred during the initial 24 h of sample curing, when a continuous structure of interconnected needles of phase 5 is formed. For Se, all measurements were below the detection limit, while Zn exhibited the highest leaching rate. Furthermore, the concentration of Zn is decreasing in time for all samples (from 24 h to 7 days). This effect can be explained by the subsequent

Fig. 10. Colorimetric data of CGD-modified MOC samples before and after surface treatment.

Table 12

The phase composition of the MOC samples with CGD in wt.%.

	Amorphous phase	SiO ₂ Quartz	Mg ₃ Cl(OH) ₅ •4H ₂ O Phase 5	Mg ₂ (CO ₃)(H ₂ O)(OH)Cl•H ₂ O Chlorartinite
MOC-REF	7	62	30	1
MOC-CGD-3	12	62	25	1
MOC-CGD-6	14	61	24	1
MOC-CGD-9	16	61	23	traces

Fig. 11. XRD patterns of the prepared MOC samples with CGD: MOC-REF, MOC-CGD-3, MOC-CGD-6, and MOC-CGD-9.

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of prepared MOC samples: MOC-REF, MOC-CGD-3, MOC-CGD-6, and MOC-CGD-9.

incorporation of Zn into the MOC matrix, where it substitutes Mg atoms. Leachate concentrations of Cd, Se, and Zn were rigorously assessed against the thresholds stipulated by Czech Ordinance No. 273/2021. This national directive establishes the regulatory limits for waste materials intended for backfilling applications or safe landfill disposal without posing an environmental risk, aligning with broader European standards for waste management and utilization. The measured values, reported in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (equivalent to ppb), were substantially below these prescribed legislative maxima for all analysed heavy metals (HMs). This robust evidence confirms the effective immobilisation of heavy metals within the formulated CGD-modified MOC composites. Consequently, these materials do not present an environmental hazard; rather, they demonstrate successful valorisation and safe utilization of the waste stream through

Fig. 13. Elemental maps of fractured surfaces of MOC samples with CGD.

Fig. 14. Reconstructed CT slices and 3D volume renderings (with aligned clipping box) of MOC samples with CGD.

efficient contaminant stabilisation.

The impact of adding CGD on the rheological properties of MOC-based composites was assessed using the Vicat needle method. The results (Fig. 15) showed that the addition of waste glass slightly affects the setting speed of the MOC mixtures; however, the overall impact on the rheological behaviour at this stage is not considerable. This is consistent with the previous observation that the addition of CGD did not actively influence the precipitation of the composites but primarily caused the refinement of the matrix. MOC-REF exhibited the fastest setting, suggesting that the presence of glass dust could slightly slow down the hydration and setting process. This effect could be advantageously utilised in the practical application of MOC-CGD compositions in construction, where workability is a critical factor in casting building components and structures. In future work and with respect to slightly decelerated hydration, the

Table 13

Leachability of Cd, Se, and Zn from the prepared MOC with CGD after 24 h and 7 days of curing.

	Concentration in leachate					
	Cd ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)		Se ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)		Zn ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	
	24 h	7 d	24 h	7 d	24 h	7 d
MOC-REF	0.08	<DL	<DL	<DL	2.72	0.56
MOC-CGD-3	0.12	0.27	<DL	<DL	4.74	0.35
MOC-CGD-6	0.45	0.67	<DL	<DL	1.04	0.43
MOC-CGD-9	0.28	0.89	<DL	<DL	3.42	0.71

Fig. 15. Measured height converted to Vicat setting time as a function of static time for CGD-modified MOC mixtures and specimen of MOC-CGD-3 produced by extrusion through a flow viscometer.

differences in hydration heat development will be investigated with a focus on the feasibility of casting massive construction elements. The development of prototypes using a flow viscometer demonstrated the suitability of the prepared cement pastes for further detailed testing and optimization for 3D printing applications. The 3D-printed samples from the MOC-CGD-3 composition which exhibited in Table 7 the highest compressive and flexural strengths when prepared as moulded specimens were tested. The prepared samples yielded compressive and flexural strengths after 7 days of 33.66 ± 2.77 MPa and 13.92 ± 1.64 MPa, respectively. The testing of prototype's compressive strength and the specimen after the testing are shown in Supporting Information (Figs. S11, S12)

4. Conclusions

This study introduces a novel valorisation route for ultra-fine coral-coloured glass dust containing Cd/Se pigments by incorporating it into magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC), rather than the more commonly studied Portland cement systems with colourless/container glass. Unlike previous work on generic glass cullet, we target a small-volume but environmentally challenging waste stream and demonstrate its safe immobilisation in a high-performance binder.

Despite the specific chemical composition of glass, its addition in amounts of 3, 6, and 9 wt% did not negatively affect the basic structural soundness, mechanical strength, or thermal performance of the resulting CGD-modified MOC-based composites.

The inclusion of CGD led to a slight refinement of the microstructure, with minimal changes in porosity and pore size distribution. Mechanical testing confirmed that all modified composites maintained compressive strength within the high-strength concrete class, making them suitable for structural applications such as prefabricated elements, industrial flooring, and façade panels. Furthermore, the composites exhibited improved water resistance, likely due to enhanced matrix packing and increased gel phase content. Although the softening coefficient was evidently improved, the obtained results can be regarded as preliminary from the standpoint of long-term durability. A comprehensive durability assessment requires additional testing, including long-term monitoring of volumetric changes under high relative humidity, evaluation of freeze–thaw resistance, and other relevant performance indicators. These analyses and investigations will be addressed in the forthcoming stages of the ongoing research.

Specifically, the distinct colour changes realised upon incorporation and subsequent polishing of the waste glass beads yield an aesthetically compelling feature that is highly relevant for contemporary interior architectural elements.

Thermal properties showed negligible differences between the reference and modified samples, indicating that the low proportion of CGD does not significantly alter the thermal behaviour of the composites. XRD and SEM analyses confirmed the preservation of the characteristic MOC Phase 5 crystalline structure and the formation of a dense, intergrown microstructure. Leaching tests revealed minimal environmental risk, with selenium levels below detection limits and only moderate zinc release during the early curing stages.

Importantly, the pilot tests confirmed the workability of the material for potential 3D printing technology. The addition of CGD slightly affected the rheological behaviour of the MOC mixtures and slightly extended the setting time. The prolonged workability

window facilitates layer-by-layer deposition and shaping, which is why further research should focus on extending the setting time depending on the chosen geometry and volume of the printed objects. The greatest application potential of 3D-printed components based on MOC-CGD composites lies primarily in construction elements that are not intended for bearing significant structural loads. These components are ideally suited for non-load-bearing partition walls and interior dividers, construction boards for interior use, decorative panels, facing slabs, and architectural elements, where 3D printing enables the creation of complex shapes and designs that would be difficult or costly to produce with traditional manufacturing methods. The precision of 3D printing also allows for rapid production of custom-fit components, minimizing waste and enabling integration of additional functionalities directly into the structural element - for example, channels for wiring, ventilation openings, or spaces for installing other systems. To fully realize this potential, however, further development and optimization of 3D printing technologies specifically tailored to the properties of MOC-CGD materials are necessary to realize the first pilot production. Overall, this research highlights the potential to valorise niche industrial waste streams, such as coloured glass dust from bead manufacturing, by integrating them into advanced, sustainable construction materials. The findings support the development of environmentally responsible MOC-based composites designed for additive manufacturing technologies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mária Kolářová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Alexandra Kloužková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martina Záleská:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Adam Pivák:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Milena Pavlíková:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christos G. Aneziris:** Investigation, Data curation. **Jana Hubalkova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Zbyšek Pavlík:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2026.115793>.

Data availability

The raw data is stored under the following DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16313543.

References

- [1] V. Lahme, O. ÓByrne, J. Carhart, How Circular is Glass?, 2022.
- [2] H. Azari Jafari, Y. Lyu, I.B. Manav, Open-Loop Recycling of Glass in Concrete Provides Upcycling Opportunities, MIT Concrete Sustainability Hub, 2022.
- [3] S. Kaza, L.C. Yao, P. Bhada Tata, F. Van Woerden, T.M.R. Martin, K.R.B. Serrona, R. Thakur, F. Pop, S. Hayashi, G. Solorzano, N.S. Alencastro Larios, R. A. Poveda, A. Ismail, What a Waste 2.0 : a Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050, Urban Development Series, World Bank Group, Washington, D. C., 2021.
- [4] Owens-Illinois, 2024 Sustainability Report Update, 2024.
- [5] Preciosa, We are a Green Company, 2025.
- [6] E. Gimenez-Carbo, L. Soriano, M. Roig-Flores, P. Serna, Characterization of glass powder from glass recycling process waste and preliminary testing, *Materials* 14 (11) (2021) 2971.
- [7] B.P. Nugraha, E.T. Sudjatmiko, I. Bali, Compressive strength of concrete containing recycled glass powder, *PRESUNIVE Civil Engineering Journal* 1 (1) (2023) 8–12.

- [8] D. Paul, K.R. Bindhu, A.M. Matos, J. Delgado, Eco-friendly concrete with waste glass powder: a sustainable and circular solution, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 355 (2022) 129217.
- [9] M. Sabbrojjaman, Y. Liu, T. Tafsirojjaman, A comparative review on the utilisation of recycled waste glass, ceramic and rubber as fine aggregate on high performance concrete: mechanical and durability properties, *Dev. Built Environ.* 17 (2024) 100371.
- [10] S.B. Olabimtan, Ö. Damdelen, Effect of waste glass powder and recycled fine aggregate in sustainable concrete, *Journal of Structural Engineering & Applied Mechanics* 6 (4) (2023) 343–363.
- [11] E. Harrison, A. Berenjhan, M. Seifan, Recycling of waste glass as aggregate in cement-based materials, *Environ Sci Ecotech* 4 (2020) 100064.
- [12] D.H. Brad, R.A. Henry, E.A. Carlos, Influence of the incorporation of recycled glass powder on the FreshState properties and compressive, tensile, and flexural strength at 7, 14, and 28 days of a sustainable concrete with $f_c = 280 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, Designed using the ACI method, in the City of Lima, *Mater. Sci. Forum* 1137 (2024) 101–109.
- [13] S.B. Nia, A. Nyland, J. Wivast, M. Kioumarsi, B. Shafei, Investigations of portland limestone cement and waste glass powder for sustainable ultra-high performance concrete, *Case Stud. Constr. Mater.* 22 (2025) e04425.
- [14] J.C. Kuri, A. Hosan, F.U.A. Shaikh, W.K. Biswas, The effect of recycled waste glass as a coarse aggregate on the properties of Portland cement concrete and geopolymer concrete, *Buildings-Basel* 13 (3) (2023) 586.
- [15] M. Mejdí, W. Wilson, M. Saillio, T. Chaussadent, L. Divet, A. Tagnit-Hamou, Investigating the pozzolanic reaction of post-consumption glass powder and the role of portlandite in the formation of sodium-rich C-S-H, *Cement Concrete Res* 123 (2019) 105790.
- [16] Z. Pavlík, M. Záleská, M. Pavlíková, A. Pivák, A.M. Lauermannová, M. Lauermannová, M. Lojka, A. Jiríčková, G. Lagód, O. Jankovsky, Utilization of extracted carbonaceous shale waste in eco-friendly cementitious blends, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 394 (2023) 132069.
- [17] M. Kolarova, A. Klouzkova, O. Jankovsky, A.M. Lauermannova, M. Zaleska, A. Pivak, M. Pavlikova, Z. Pavlik, The effect of application of waste glass cullet as a filler in a cleaner production of magnesium oxychloride cement composites, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 482 (2025) 141649.
- [18] H.K.D.H. Bhadeshia, Additive manufacturing, *Mater Sci Tech-Lond* 32 (7) (2016) 615–616.
- [19] D.M. Hajare, T.S. Gajbhiye, Additive manufacturing (3D printing): recent progress on advancement of materials and challenges, *Mater. Today Proc.* 58 (2022) 736–743.
- [20] N. Vidakis, C. David, M. Petousis, D. Sagris, N. Mountakis, A. Moutsopoulou, The effect of six key process control parameters on the surface roughness, dimensional accuracy, and porosity in material extrusion 3D printing of polylactic acid: prediction models and optimization supported by robust design analysis, *Adv Ind Manuf Eng* 5 (2022) 100104.
- [21] N. Vidakis, M. Petousis, J.D. Kechagias, Parameter effects and process modelling of polyamide 12 3D-printed parts strength and toughness, *Mater. Manuf. Process.* 37 (11) (2022) 1358–1369.
- [22] P. Ravi, L.L. Chepelev, G. Stichweh, B.S. Jones, F.J. Rybicki, Medical 3D printing dimensional accuracy for multi-pathological anatomical models 3D printed using material extrusion, *J Digit Imaging* 35 (3) (2022) 613–622.
- [23] J. Pierre, F. Iervolino, R.D. Farahani, N. Piccirelli, M. Lévesque, D. Therriault, Material extrusion additive manufacturing of multifunctional sandwich panels with load-bearing and acoustic capabilities for aerospace applications, *Addit. Manuf.* 61 (2023) 103344.
- [24] Z.U. Arif, M.Y. Khalid, R. Noroozi, A. Sadeghianmaryan, M. Jalalvand, M. Hossain, Recent advances in 3D-printed polylactide and polycaprolactone-based biomaterials for tissue engineering applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 218 (2022) 930–968.
- [25] M. Gupta, 3D printing of metals, *Metals-Basel* 7 (10) (2017) 403.
- [26] W.Q. Wang, W.Q. Liu, G. Cao, X.C. Cui, Y.Z. Lu, J. Cheng, Additive manufacturing of cemented carbide by material extrusion, *J Alloy Compd* 1026 (2025).
- [27] Y. Lakhdar, C. Tuck, J. Binner, A. Terry, R. Goodridge, Additive manufacturing of advanced ceramic materials, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 116 (2021) 100736.
- [28] J.A. Inzana, D. Olvera, S.M. Fuller, J.P. Kelly, O.A. Graeve, E.M. Schwarz, S.L. Kates, H.A. Awad, 3D printing of composite calcium phosphate and collagen scaffolds for bone regeneration, *Biomaterials* 35 (13) (2014) 4026–4034.
- [29] A. Perrot, D. Rangeard, A. Pierre, Structural built-up of cement-based materials used for 3D-printing extrusion techniques, *Mater. Struct.* 49 (4) (2016) 1213–1220.
- [30] G. Cruz, J.R.C. Dizon, N. Farzadnia, H.Y. Zhou, M. Margarito, J.A. Garcia, F.P. Liza, R.C. Advincula, Performance, applications, and sustainability of 3D-printed cement and other geomaterials, *MRS Commun.* 13 (3) (2023) 385–399.
- [31] V.N. Nerella, S. Hempel, V. Mechtcherine, Micro- and macroscopic investigations on the interface between layers of 3D-printed cementitious elements. International Conference on Advances in Construction Materials and Systems, Chennai, 2017, pp. 1–10.
- [32] M. Hambach, D. Volkmer, Properties of 3D-printed fiber-reinforced Portland cement paste, *Cement Concrete Comp* 79 (2017) 62–70.
- [33] M. Petousis, N. Michailidis, V. Kulas, V. Papadakis, M. Spiridaki, N. Mountakis, A. Argyros, J. Valsamos, E. Stratakis, N. Vidakis, Valorization of recycled fine powder glass (RFPG) in additive manufacturing: optimization of the RFPG content in polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) and multi-response analysis, *Clean. Mater.* 14 (2024) 100271.
- [34] N. Vidakis, M. Petousis, N. Mountakis, V. Papadakis, C. Charou, V. Rousos, P. Bastas, Glass fillers in three different forms used as reinforcement agents of polylactic acid in material extrusion additive manufacturing, *Appl Sci-Basel* 13 (11) (2023) 6471.
- [35] M. Petousis, N. Michailidis, V. Papadakis, N. Mountakis, A. Argyros, M. Spiridaki, A. Moutsopoulou, N.K. Nasikas, N. Vidakis, The impact of the glass microparticles features on the engineering response of isotactic polypropylene in material extrusion 3D printing, *Mater. Today Commun.* 37 (2023) 107204.
- [36] A. Boleslavsky, H. Ovcáčková, M. Mihola, A. Mikkola, M. Topinková, Z. Bobovsky, Study of 3D printing process: optimization, quality analysis, and comparison of 3D printed and cast ceramic properties, *Open Ceramics* 23 (2025) 100797.
- [37] A. Klouzková, P. Dvořáková, M. Kolářová, V. Kulas, Studie recyklace odpadu z výroby barevných perliček keramickou cestou, *Sklar a Keram.* 1–2 (2025) 3–7.
- [38] A.M. Lauermannova, M. Lojka, J. Sklenka, M. Zaleska, M. Pavlikova, A. Pivak, Z.E. Pavlik, O. Jankovsky, Magnesium oxychloride-graphene composites: towards high strength and water resistant materials for construction industry, *FlatChem* 29 (2021) 100284.
- [39] C.H. Lin, J.K. Zhou, Equivalent confining stress-based strength model for concrete under triaxial compression, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 372 (2023) 130812.
- [40] Q. Huang, W.X. Zheng, X.Y. Xiao, J.M. Dong, J. Wen, C.G. Chang, Effects of fly ash, phosphoric acid, and nano-silica on the properties of magnesium oxychloride cement, *Ceram. Int.* 47 (24) (2021) 34341–34351.
- [41] A.M. Lauermannova, M. Lojka, O. Chmel, O. Jankovsky, M. Zaleska, A. Pivak, M. Pavlikova, Z. Pavlik, Silicate refractory brick waste as quartz sand filler replacement in MOC-based composites, *Case Stud. Constr. Mater.* 22 (2025) e04156.
- [42] O. Jankovsky, M. Lojka, A.M. Lauermannová, F. Antončík, M. Pavlíková, Z. Pavlík, D. Sedmidubsky, Carbon dioxide uptake by MOC-based materials, *Appl Sci-Basel* 10 (7) (2020) 2254.